

8T – On Gravity and Acceleration

"I know what it means to know something." Richard Feynman.

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the 8T which validate the idea of equivalence between gravity and acceleration, author will try to reason why it is so by nature. The idea is to ensure that the arbitrary variation will reach the minima in minimal time. to reach the minimal time, nature will try to attain maximal speed, i.e. the acceleration.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Up to this point was introduction, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **paper**. we are familiar with the famous idea of Einstein, which state that there exist a morphism among gravity or curvature and acceleration. That is preciously the idea behind the main equation of the 8T, equation (1).

$$\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial g}{\partial t}$$

The question in which one will try to answer is the following: can we go further in reasoning this relation? Can we explain why it has to be that way? and do it in a simple manner which do not involve further complications equation wise. The author believes that it is possible to do using the framework of calculus of variations. To do just that we can imagine an arbitrary variation cluster which has mass, falling onto the curvature spike non vanishing. We can make an theorem and according to this theorem we can reason the relation of the main equation (1):

Theorem (1.2): nature would aspire that a fermion cluster falling into a curvature spike will reach the minima in minimal time.

That is similar to Fermat principle of least time but in a different context. Now, the key point is the following: for the fermion cluster to reach the minima of the curvature spike in minimal time, it has to gain maximal speed, which is the integration of the acceleration.

$$v = \int \frac{d^2x}{dt^2}$$

Therefore, to reach the lowest point of the curve in the minimal time, nature would accelerate the falling body to a maximal speed. It is somewhat different from the equivalence principle as it puts a cause and a result relation among those two, but that is precisely the point of the paper. Can we explain **why** there is a morphism between those two terms? Using extremum value demand on time allows us to reason it in terms of cause and effect. Such is needed, as up to this point in time, we are able to reason it exist, Einstein proved it first in the 20-th century, but as far as one knows, the question of why was not answered. Summing up, nature is governed by creation of extremum values, based on theorem (1.2) a body falling into a curvature spike would aspire to reach the minima at $t \rightarrow 0$ and to do just that nature would aspire it's speed to reach another extremum, $v \rightarrow 1$. Theorem (1.2) could be regarded as the reason for the equivalence principle according to the author.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

Manor Ohad